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CONTENTS

- Impact of Psychological factors on Self-regulation among Indian Adolescent Examinees 1
Harmeet Kaur, Dr. Harpreet Kanwal Chhabra
- Competency in Malayalam among B.Ed. Students in Kerala 7
Dr. K. Abdul Gafoor, Sujilarani. V.M
- A Study of Problems of Students and Teachers of the Special Schools for Hearing Impairment .. 14
Prof. R. G. Kothari, Mr. H. S. Mistry
- Regional Imbalances in Educational Facilities in Rural Areas:
A Case Study of Malda District (West Bengal) 22
Nazmul Hussain
- Teachers' Attitudes towards Inclusive Education System:
An Exploratory Study of University and Secondary School Teachers 32
Seema Sharma, Dr. Seema Sharma
- Use of Information and Communication Technology for Homework by the Students 37
Geeta Kapoor
- In-Service Programmes for Primary Teachers 46
Prof. R.G. Kothari, Dr. Jignesh B. Patel
- Major Intervention Programmes Implemented Among
Juvenile Delinquents to Correct Their Behaviour 51
Dr. Sreekala K.K., Anilakumari. M.C
- Education in India in the Age of Globalisation: Present Scenario & Challenges Ahead 55
Shri Kant Dwivedi, Md. Firoz Alam
- Relationship of Gender, Qualification and Experience on Teaching Competency:
An Exploratory Study of Eritrean Teachers 61
Dr. Harish Kumar Tyagi
- Association of Religion with Attitude towards Multimedia 66
Manika Sharma
- Education loan- An effective tool for the expansion of higher Education in India 70
Prof. Lokesh Sharma, Nikhilesh C Sharma, Parul D. Aggarwal
- Development and Try-out of a Creativity Programme for
Pre-service Teachers at Primary Level in English 75
Dr. Satish P. Pathak
- Research Abstract 80
- Book Review 87

A Study of Problems of Students and Teachers of the Special Schools for Hearing Impairment

*Prof. R. G. Kothari

**Mr. H. S. Mistry

INTRODUCTION

Inherent in the philosophy of democracy is the right of all children to develop to their maximum potential. Public education in different nations has been founded on the preposition that educational opportunities must be provided to all children who can benefit from them so that they develop to their maximum potential. The goal of providing education to the disabled children and rehabilitating the group of the persons with disability has been taken up seriously only recently in India. recognition of the need for educational services to the disabled as a human right just like any other citizen and the goal of Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) have strongly pulled the educators and planners towards special educational services for the children with disability. Providing access to basic education is a duty the Indian state that has taken upon itself. Therefore the government has taken various measures to provide access to education to all categories of students. Thus the children with disability are provided special education in India so that they can seriously engage in improving the quality of their life. Research studies in special education for the disabled are very few indeed. Jangira and Mukhopadhyay (1991) mentioned the reason for low yield as the university departments and apex organizations like the National Council of Educational Research & Training (NCERT), National Institute of Educational Planning & Administration (NIEPA) and University Grant Commission (UGC) remained alienated from special education. The organizations working under the umbrella of welfare activities lacked capabilities for research. Some research did emerge in rehabilitation centres, but the

The purpose of the present investigation was to study the problems of students and teachers of the special schools for the hearing impaired. 3 special schools for the hearing impaired of Gujarat were selected randomly. 10 teachers and 42 students with hearing impairment from standard IX were selected randomly. The study revealed many problems of students and teachers of the special schools for the hearing impairment.

Abstract

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focus of such research has been on diagnosis and medical aspects, not on special education. With the Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) scheme being transferred to the Department of Education in the Ministry of Human Resource & Development (MHRD) and the consequent involvement of the NCERT, UGC, NIEPA and universities in development and training activities, research activities in special education are expected to improve in range and quality. The misconception which has impeded research in special education is that the problems of education of disabled person do not transcend the boundaries of psychology.

In the area of education of the children with Hearing Impairment (HI), only six studies (Kapoor, 1990; Mandke (1991; Paranjpe, 1991; Sharma, 1989, Sahoo, 1991 and Sharma & Panday, 1992) could be located till fifth survey while only three studies (Reddy, 1993; Shivji, 1995 and Pandit, 1996) were conducted during the period of sixth survey of educational research. Bala, (1985), Mandke (1991) Sahoo (1991) and Goel (1986) covered hearing impaired as a subsample. Reddy (1993) measured effect of physical education programme on motor behavior of the students with hearing impairment while Shivji (1995) and Pandit (1996) studied structural and functional aspects of organization of HI and basic vocabulary in Gujarati of HI student respectively. Out of the total nine studies, Bala, 1985 and Goel, 1986 were compared hearing-impaired children with non-hearing-impaired children on selected variables. Six of the nine studies had taken sample from integrated education while only one study of Shivji (1995) was based on the students of special schools. No single study found on the problems of students as well as teachers of special schools for the HI. Therefore, there is need to undertake a study that focuses upon the administrative & organizational setup, enrollment & dropout of students, problems of teachers & students of the special schools for the HI.

From the review of the related literature it was also revealed that very few studies have been taken relating to education of children with HI and based on the sixth survey, no any study has been conducted after the year 1996 on children with HI. It is also noted that attempt was made in some studies

to compare the nature, choice, interest and academic achievement of children with HI and children with non-HI. Only study of Mukhopadhyay & Sharma (1990) focused on the problem of identifying competences in integrated setting but no any study have been conducted on the problems of students and teachers of a special schools of HI. Therefore, the present study is an attempt in this direction to study the problems of teachers and students in different dimensions.

Hence, looking into these all, it is felt by the researchers that there is a need to conduct a study which can focus only on students and teachers of special schools for children with hearing impairment and present a detailed picture of interpretation, finding and suggestions. Therefore the present study has been undertaken by the researchers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A Study of the Problems of Students and Teachers of the Special Schools for Hearing Impairment

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To study the organizational & administration set-up of the special schools in terms of
 - Physical Facilities
 - Financial Services
 - Staff Composition
 - Teacher-Pupil Ratio
 - Number of Pupils Enrolled
 - Number of pupils dropped out
 - Vocational Training to the Students,
 - Activities,
 - Problems,
 - Syllabus,
 - Linking with General Schools
 - Affiliation with Higher Education Institution

- 2) To study the problems of the teachers of special schools.
- 3) To study the problems of the students of special schools.
- 4) To study the needs to overcome the problems of teachers and students of special schools.

EXPLANATION OF THE TERM

- **Special Schools:** For the present study, special schools means the schools for hearing impaired either managed by government or private trusts. By this definition, the scope of the term special schools is limited to the schools for the children with hearing impairment.

DELIMITATION

- The present study is delimited to the secondary section of the special schools for the hearing impaired of the Gujarat state only.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

The present study is survey type in nature.

POPULATION

The population of the present study comprised of 15 special schools for the children with hearing impairment of the Gujarat. Also all the students and teachers of the special schools were considered as population for the present study.

SAMPLE

Out of the total fifteen special schools for the children with hearing impairment located in Gujarat, three special schools for the children with hearing impairment viz. Shree K. L. Institute for the Deaf, Bhavnagar; Lt. D. P. A. Shah School for the Deaf, Surat and Smt. Kamlababen Badhvir Vidyalaya, Vadodara has been selected randomly as a sample for the present study. For selecting sample of teachers, ten teachers (six male and four female) has been selected randomly while for the sample of students total forty two students with hearing impairment (thirty male and twelve female) of standard IX has been selected randomly.

TOOLS

Considering the objectives of the present study, three tools viz, *information schedule for the school principal*, *questionnaire for the teachers* and *questionnaire for the students* were prepared to collect the required data for the study. Researchers had reviewed recent researchers conducted in the field and prepared the tools in Gujarat as the medium of the instruction in respondent schools in the Gujarat. The prepared tools were sent to the experts in the field for its validation. Necessary modifications were done as per the suggestions received from the experts. The finally prepared tools were referred to Gujarati language experts for language corrections and accordingly necessary modifications and changes made as per the suggestions of language experts.

The *Information schedule* comprised total seventy items regarding the information related to the special school for hearing impairment, different activities, facilities available and their problems, enrollment and dropout figure of the students for the current year (2010-11), details of the teachers working, teacher-pupil ratio, in-service training to teachers. The *Questionnaire for the teachers* had total forty five close ended and open ended items including questions related to teaching process, training received, problems facing, and their needs to overcome their problems. The *Questionnaire for the students* had total eighty nine close ended and open ended items which was prepared with keeping in mind about the questions related to their personnel and family background, academic, social, economic and other problems and their needs to overcome their problems.

DATA COLLECTION

Data were collected in four phases. In the first phase, the investigators had mailed *information schedule* tool to all the eleven special schools. In the second phase, the co-investigator *personally met* to the school principal of the respondent special schools and requested for collecting data from the teachers of secondary section and standard IX students. In the third phase, the investigators *personally met* to each and every teachers of secondary section of the selected special school and collected the required data from them

fathers (9.52 percent) and mothers (2.38 percent) of the students were studied upto higher secondary school or above.

- The objective vocationalization of secondary education is not achieving at desired level in special schools as only 7.14 percent of the respondent students of special schools were engaged in vocational training. To provide vocational education to these students is urgent required for diversifying these students in some vocation as majority of the students (95.23 percent) did not like to study and, wanted to join some vocation for earning. Linkage between special schools and some NGOs can be benefited for this.
- Majority of the students (64.28 percent) did not receive any type of scholarships and also facing financial problems. Government should provide scholarships with proper amount to all the students of special schools so they can complete their education without any financial constraint.
- Majority of the students (61.91 percent) were reading extra materials in their leisure time and 73.81 percent of the students were having wish to continue their till higher education so self study printed materials can be developed same as available in correspondence courses so they can develop self study habits and also burdens of teachers could be minimized.
- Majority of the students (71.42 percent) did not have much problems in study but most of the students (95.23 percent) did not like to study, felt the secondary syllabus too lengthy for study (69.04 percent) and their impairment affecting in their study (61.90percent) so educational think tank must revise the syllabus with keeping in mind the level and impairment of the students

of special schools which is also suggested by the teachers.

- Family (47.61 percent) and teachers (45.23 percent) were the main source for the help in the study of students of special schools but 83.33percent) felt the teaching methods of the teachers unsuitable so to provide in-service training to teachers can be benefited.
- 38.09 percent of the respondent students were not getting adequate financial support for their study. Government should be provided scholarship with proper amount to these students which can be great help for overcoming financial difficulties for their study.
- Most of the students (90.47 percent) were not having social problems and they were receiving teacher's support for solving their social problems.

Needs of Teachers and Students

Both the teachers and students of the special schools were having needs as per their problems. Disability level wise distribution of students, awareness in parents, hearing aids to all special school children, integration of special students in general school after achieving needed skills, appointment of enough number teachers for different subjects, availability of enough facilities and modern technology, good salary alongwith other facilities and allowances, proper support from government, availability of vocational courses were the needs of teachers of the special schools for overcoming their problems while extra coaching, mobility/transport facility, motivation for participating in different activities and sports, vocational education with secure job, reduction in current syllabus were the academic needs of the students of the special schools. Students were having financial need of providing educational loan and financial assistance for their education. Social awareness regarding the hearing impairment and socially acceptance from others were the social needs of the students of the special schools.

CONCLUSION

A quality system same as that of general education is also very essential in achieving the goal of education for all in

country. The present study revealed problems of teachers and students like less number of special schools, unavailability of grants and required facilities, less number of teachers in special schools, lack of in-service training, very less salary of teachers and students' uninterest towards study, unawareness in parents, hearing aids for all children of special school, integration of special students in general school after achieving needed skills, appointment of enough number teachers for different subjects, availability of enough facilities and modern technology, good salary, proper support from government, availability of vocational courses were the suggestions to overcome the problems of teachers of special schools while extra coaching, mobility/transport facility, vocational education with secure job, reduction in current syllabus, providing educational loan and financial assistance, and social awareness were the needs of students of special schools. Now it is the time for the planners and authorities of education in general and special education in particular to solve the problems of teachers and students. It is very important to provide the required grants and facilities for the betterment of the children of the special schools. The focus is needed in this sector of education which in turn will help to achieve the objective of universalization of secondary education.

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Book Review

Mathematics Weaknesses among Secondary School Students

*Mr. H. S. Mistry

**Ms. Monika Puri

Lack of mastery among students in basic operations of mathematics like addition, subtraction, multiplication and division leads to poor achievement and negative attitude towards mathematics. The knowledge about the students' weaknesses in mathematics can be useful to the teachers for planning their teaching and for providing remedial measures which can improve the quality of mathematics education.

The same attempt is made by the VDM, Publishing House Ltd., Meldrum Court 17, Beau Bassin, Mauritius, by publishing the book titled **Mathematics Weaknesses among Secondary School Students** in current year 2011. This book is based on the research study conducted by **Prof. R. G. Kothari** and **Ms. Prerana Shelat**. Prof. R. G. Kothari (Former Vice Chancellor of South Gujarat University, Surat; Former Head, CASE, & Dean, Faculty of Education & Psychology, The M. S. University of Baroda, Vadodara) is a well known Professor of Education and Ms. Prerana Shelat is a Assistant Professor in Education, CASE who is also working for her doctoral study in the area of Science Teaching. Through this book, the authors highlighted the major weaknesses in mathematics among secondary school students.

Published book contains Mathematical Weaknesses Test constructed by the authors for the purpose of studying the

mathematics weaknesses among the secondary school students. The standardized test covers 70 items based on the topics of Standard V, VI and VII and implemented on 737 students in 29 secondary schools of Vadodara city. The test was highly reliable as the test-retest and split half reliability of the test was found to be 0.67 and 0.71 respectively. The result of the study revealed that the students of Central Board of Secondary Education schools have least weaknesses, English medium school students had less weaknesses than the Gujarati medium students, no impact of additional coaching on mathematics achievement, BODMAS (First open the bracket then do the division then only multiply followed by addition and finally subtraction) was the most difficult item and subtraction of two decimal numbers where subtraction did not involve any borrowing was the easiest item in the test. The book also covers discussion by the authors about the major findings of the study.

In all, this book will be helpful to the mathematics teachers in general and secondary school mathematics teachers in particular for knowing the weaknesses of students in the basic concepts of mathematics and planning the teaching accordingly.

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